

TECHNOLOGIES OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY.

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Abstract: The article describes the conditions for the formation of the readiness of the future teacher of technology for a creative educational environment, which is achieved by improving the pedagogical conditions and content of training, as well as the inclusion of innovative technologies in the lesson.

Keywords: Education, condition, educational environment, innovative technologies, future teachers of technology, teacher, creative process.

Main part: into a single educational space in Europe, caused the emergence of a new social order for a teacher capable of carrying out innovative professional activities. Among the factors that determine the need to revise national priorities in the system of professional teacher training, three groups can be distinguished. First of all, these are systemic changes in national education associated with introduction of a new educational paradigm, with a transition to new content and structure general secondary education, with the introduction of state educational standards, with the transition of high school to specialized education. The success of education reform initiated at the state level is largely determined by the teacher's personal attitude towards innovation, their theoretical, methodological and practical orientation. Another group of reasons for the modernization of education consists of socio-pedagogical changes in the general secondary education system that occur in the context of transformations caused by the new socio-technological revolution. Before modern education faces a number of challenges, one of which is that national educational systems must acquire an innovative character, and their students must be prepared for innovative lifestyle. In these conditions, the readiness of teachers to accept progressive innovative changes in culture, society and education are of particular importance. Only a teacher with high creative potential is able to develop a personality capable of successful and effective life in a dynamically developing society. The third group of factors reflects the most characteristic features of the processes of broad innovative transformations. Currently, many teaching staff of educational institutions are actively testing domestic and foreign educational technologies, creating proprietary schools, developing and introducing proprietary ones into the educational process training programs, methods, technologies, etc. For this reason, an important component of a teacher's professionalism is the readiness to evaluate the effectiveness of new pedagogical technologies. A modern teacher must be able to determine the compliance of proposed new technologies with the needs and capabilities of a particular educational institution. Professional skills of the future pedagogue-educator are effective for school education of children allows preparation. Pedagogical activities of educators, psychological, organizational-methodical learning results of students personal qualities of the pedagogue-educator and his professional training is of great importance. Accordingly, a pedagogue is an educator having professional skills, knowledge and creativity is a conscious activity in students and is the main factor of independence. Pedagogical practice The work of the future pedagogue-educator in the school is in them is important in the formation of professional skills. Future pedagogues-educators to their profession during pedagogical practice inclination, creative approach to pedagogical activity, modern knowledge acquired by him application in practical experience, acquisition of leadership skills, student personality pedagogical-psychological study, analysis, cultural public events skills such as mastering organization methods are activated and is strengthened. All this prepares students for educational activities. In addition, future pedagogic

teachers during their professional activities they also need to master a number of rules that apply.

They are:

- formation of conscious discipline in students;
- fair treatment of children;
- support and help active students in the group;
- appropriate stimulation of independent activities of students;

Conclusion: At the present stage of development of higher education, the problem of training future technology teachers who are proficient in computer technology is acquiring particular importance due to the high rates of development and improvement of science and technology, the need of society for people able to quickly navigate in an environment capable of thinking independently and free from stereotypes. The use of these technologies in the training of labor education is also explained by the need to solve the problem of finding ways and means of enhancing the cognitive interest of students, developing their creative abilities, and stimulating mental activity. A feature of the educational process with the use of computer tools is that the student becomes the center of activity, who, proceeding from his individual abilities and interests, builds up the process of knowledge. A “subject-subjective” relationship develops between the teacher and the student. The teacher often acts as an assistant, consultant, encouraging original finds, stimulating activity, initiative and independence.

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